

Trade agreements and environmental provisions: a counterfactual analysis of environmental impact shifting under global economic inequality

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ABSTRACT

Regional trade agreements (RTAs) have proliferated in recent decades, with increasingly stringent environmental clauses aimed at mitigating trade impacts. However, studies on the environmental effects of RTAs typically focus on a few agreements and indicators, hindering a comprehensive understanding of their effects across various resources. Additionally, the long-term effectiveness of environmental provisions within RTAs remains unclear. To address this gap, we applied a rigorous counterfactual analysis to evaluate changes in multiple resource footprints associated with RTAs and environmental provisions across 195 countries annually from 1990 to 2018. We examined four key resources: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. Findings revealed that RTAs were linked to the outsourcing of environmental footprints across all resource types while reducing footprint insourcing, a phenomenon known as environmental impact shifting. This effect was particularly evident in wealthier countries, where outsourcing of primary energy, primarily from lower-income nations, rose by 11.6%, raw materials by 13.6%, and land use by 33.5%, compared to similar non-RTA countries. Furthermore, these countries' insourcing of primary energy was reduced by 48.3% and blue water by 15.4% relative to non-RTA counterparts. Environmental provisions within RTAs had limited long-term effectiveness in reducing environmental footprints outsourcing. Global trends show a growing disparity in resource use between wealthy and poor countries, exacerbated by RTAs. Rigorous footprint accounting and a resource-equity mechanism, including ecological premiums for resource-intensive imports, are essential within RTAs. Wealthier nations must adopt more accountable consumption-based governance, prioritising reductions in material consumption to alleviate the socio-ecological impacts on poorer countries.

1. Introduction

International trade is widely seen as crucial for global prosperity (OECD, 2023; The World Bank, 2018). The dominant view in global policy circles is that economic growth is necessary to finance development and transitions to environmental sustainability, e.g. decarbonisation. However, this perspective is also extensively criticised in terms of the problematic relationship between trade, economic growth, inequality, and planetary environmental boundaries and cascading tipping points (Franzke et al., 2022; Humpenöder et al., 2022), as well as differential responsibilities for the socio-ecological impacts of trade. Trade has played a key role in economic globalisation of the twentieth century, and the number of Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) have proliferated in recent decades. RTAs are reciprocal trade agreements between two or more partner states aiming to reduce tariffs (import and export duties) and/or other trade barriers between the parties. RTAs

constitute one of the allowed exemptions from the World Trade Organisation's (WTO's) core principle of non-discrimination between trading partners, though they are subject to a number of WTO requirements for notification and transparency. As of February 2024, a total of 365 Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) are in effect, encompassing arrangements such as Free Trade Agreement (FTA), Customs Union (CU), Economic Integration Agreement (EIA), and Partial Scope Agreement (PSA) (World Trade Organization, 2024).

Numerous studies have explored the societal and environmental impacts of trade (Friel et al., 2020; Roux et al., 2021; Wiedmann and Lenzen, 2018), but much less has been carried out specifically on the environmental impacts of RTAs. Existing research tends to concentrate on a limited number of RTAs (Nemati et al., 2019) and emphasises economic outcomes, such as trade volumes (Kohl, 2014; Nguyen, 2019) and investment flows (Duong et al., 2021; Larch and Yotov, 2024), revealing that RTAs often boost imports in participating countries and

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encourage investments in producing nations (Duong et al., 2021). However, there is a lack of comprehensive assessments of RTAs' resource footprints, the social and environmental costs, associated with traded goods. Most studies focus on isolated indicators, such as deforestation, pollution, or carbon emissions (Abman and Lundberg, 2020; Le et al., 2016; Nemati et al., 2019), and typically find that RTAs exacerbate pollution and emissions in less affluent producing countries (Halicioglu and Ketenci, 2016; Nemati et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2022). The outsourcing of resource-intensive production to these nations frequently results in environmental degradation and social inequities, often due to inadequate governance structures (Le et al., 2016; Suárez-Varela and Rodríguez-Crespo, 2022). Understanding the socio-environmental costs of RTAs across numerous resource indicators is crucial, since ignoring them may perpetuate socio-ecological exploitation and hinder progress toward achieving global sustainability and climate change mitigation objectives (Baccini, 2019; Felbermayr et al., 2024; Friel et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2022).

Social and environmental provisions in RTAs are a mechanism designed to mitigate negative impacts of trade agreement or to strengthen positive ones (Mattoo et al., 2020). These provisions have become more stringent in recent years (Blümer et al., 2020; Morin et al., 2018). While some see potential in such provisions (Berger et al., 2020; Brandi and Morin, 2023; Kehoe et al., 2020), there has been a lack of thorough evaluation on their effectiveness (Brandi et al., 2020). Previous studies have either contrasted the presence of environmental provision to its absence (Abman et al., 2024; Hoekman et al., 2023), covered only key countries (<60 of OECD and major developing nations) (Baghdadi et al., 2013; Martínez-Zarzoso and Oueslati, 2018; Yuan et al., 2023), been limited to a single environmental measure (Abman et al., 2024; Martínez-Zarzoso and Oueslati, 2018; Yu et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2023), or been based on outdated data (before 2011) (Baghdadi et al., 2013; Bastiaens and Postnikov, 2017; Martínez-Zarzoso and Oueslati, 2018; Zhou et al., 2017). The findings of these studies are mixed. Some indicate a decline in imports of environmentally harmful commodities (such as steel, cement, or chemicals) (Brandi et al., 2020) or a reduction in the environmental impact following the adoption of RTAs with environmental provisions (Yu et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2017), while others report marginal effects (Presberger and Bernauer, 2023; Sorgho and Tharakan, 2022). Notably, none of these studies have investigated the influence of such provisions over an extended period beyond the second year of adoption. Given that environmental provisions are often highlighted as a crucial strategy for reducing trade-related environmental impacts (Bellmann and Bulatnikova, 2022; Berger et al., 2020), it is crucial to assess their potential effectiveness over the long term.

To address the limits of earlier research, here we present novel comprehensive assessment of the global use and exchange of natural resources embodied in traded goods in relation to RTAs and the strength of environmental provisions across 195 nations annually between 1990 and 2018. We examined a range of key resource footprints: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. We evaluated the impact of environmental provisions in RTAs on footprints up to four years after adoption, providing a clearer understanding of how impacts vary over time. We sought to answer three related questions: (1) What are the trends in resource footprints and trade globally, regardless of RTA, including patterns of footprints overall and by resource origin (insourced vs outsourced), and the socioeconomic features of the trading countries? (2) How do RTAs affect countries' footprints, either those outsourced or insourced? (3) Do stronger environmental clauses in RTAs reduce the outsourcing of footprints by countries, and is this effect sustained in the long term? For resource footprints, we utilised the recently developed and currently most comprehensive multi-regional input-output data GLORIA (Global Resource Input-Output Assessment) (Lenzen et al. 2022). For the strength of environmental provisions within RTAs, we used recent data by Santika et al. (2024),

In addition to broadening the scope of previous research, we

employed a rigorous counterfactual analysis to evaluate the impact of RTAs and environmental provisions. Specifically, we employed a difference-in-differences (DID) regression coupled with non-parametric matching method (Fig. 1). Although this approach is commonly used to evaluate the effectiveness of development programs, it has rarely been applied to assess the impacts of RTAs (Abman et al., 2024; Nie et al., 2022). The 'counterfactual' assesses the potential trade flow outcomes for countries in the absence of an RTA by comparing the actual trade flows observed under the RTA with those of a control group that does not participate in an RTA. Given that countries engaged in specific RTA arrangements may differ in key characteristics (e.g., GDP, geographical location) from those that are not, it is essential to account for these differences through matching to allow apples-to-apples comparisons. Using matching, we were able to investigate variations in RTAs' impact on environmental footprints among nations with varying economic statuses. Because RTAs were implemented at different times, and various signatory countries may have joined or left at different stages (e.g. EU enlargement and Brexit), it is crucial to match these countries to specific control groups and time periods for incorporation into the DID analysis. This method also allows us to investigate how the effects of RTAs and their environmental provisions evolve over time after their implementation.

2. Theory

The theoretical framework underpinning our study builds upon three interconnected themes: (1) the environmental footprints of countries in the context of global economic inequality; (2) the influence of trade liberalisation through RTAs on these distributional dynamics; and (3) the influence of environmental clauses in RTAs in reshaping or reinforcing these patterns.

2.1. Footprints in territorial versus global systems under inequality

In policy analysis and economics, great attention is paid to the relationship between economic development and the environment. A widely used framework for this inquiry is the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) (Beckerman, 1992; Panayotou, 1993). It posits an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation, with environmental degradation increases during the initial stages of economic development but decreases once a country attains higher income levels and can invest in cleaner technologies and adopt more efficient environmental regulations (Dasgupta et al., 2006; Panayotou, 1993). However, a key assumption of this theory is that environmental impacts are primarily contained within territorial borders (relying on production-based accounting) and overlooking both global interdependence and inequality (Kaika and Zervas, 2013; Makarov and Alataş, 2024). Empirical analyses show that increasing wealth and consumer demand frequently result in the outsourcing of environmental resources (Haberl et al., 2023; Peters et al., 2021).

With the increasing adoption of life cycle assessment and consumption-based accounting, which track environmental impacts beyond national borders, the EKC hypothesis is facing growing scrutiny (Bagliani et al., 2008; Makarov and Alataş, 2024). Research reveals that in an unequal globalised economy, many high-income countries shift a large share of their environmental burdens onto lower-income nations (Fu et al., 2023; Hertwich, 2021; Liu et al., 2017). At the global level, this undermines the EKC's better promise that economic growth leads to reduced environmental degradation. These findings challenge the EKC's optimistic narrative by showing that environmental pressures are not necessarily alleviated through growth, but merely displaced. Taking this into account, our first hypothesis is therefore:

H1: *As countries develop economically, their resource consumption increases, with high-income nations offshoring a significant portion of their environmental footprints overseas.*

Fig. 1. Counterfactual analysis framework applied in this study. Difference-in-differences (DID) coupled with non-parametric matching method used to evaluate: (a) the effect of RTA on the change in footprint outsourcing (IRF) of countries, (b) the effect of RTA on the change in footprint insourcing (DRF) of countries, and (c) the effect of the stringency of environmental provisions in RTAs (“strong” or “medium” provisions versus “weak”, “very weak” or no provisions) on the change in footprint outsourcing (IRF) of countries two years after the RTA implementation. Positive value for the DID implies that the RTA or environmental provision was associated with an increase in outsourcing or insourcing of footprint compared to control, whereas negative value implies a decrease. Resource footprint indicators evaluated include the primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

2.2. Trade liberalisation through RTAs and footprint dynamics

RTAs are key to international trade. By reducing or removing tariffs and non-tariff barriers between participants, RTAs lead to the promotion

of more integrated and wider-reaching transnational transactions. Yet, their influence extends beyond just trade volumes, as they significantly reconfigure the geographical and environmental impacts of production, consumption, and resource utilisation. Studies have shown that through

this preferential market access mechanism, RTAs promote specialisation on the basis of comparative advantage that leads to significant supply chain reconfiguration as industries move to countries that can offer cost efficiencies, favourable infrastructure, or regulatory lax (Anderer et al., 2020; Antràs and Staiger, 2012; Osgood, 2018). In many cases, these encourage outsourcing of resource- and emission-intensive industries (Dellachiesa and Myint, 2016; Tian et al., 2022).

The environmental impact of RTAs often depends on the economic strength and institutional capacity of the countries involved, two factors that are typically intertwined. The pathways through which these effects unfold are outlined in Fig. 2a. In developed economies, RTAs often improve domestic environmental outcomes due to strong institutions, public demand for environmental standards, and multilateral cooperation, although they can also shift emissions abroad (Jönsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Wang and Kuusi, 2024). In contrast, low-income countries frequently face challenges in realising these benefits, as weak institutions, limited access to clean technologies, and a focus on short-term economic growth can undermine the implementation of rigorous environmental regulations (de LT Oliveira and Hecht, 2017; Zografos and Robbins, 2020). Consequently, they may experience greater environmental harm, such as resource overexploitation, expansion of polluting industries, and continued dependence on high-emission sectors. Considering this, our second hypothesis is therefore:

H2: The environmental effects of RTAs vary by economic status, with high-income countries gaining the most. These nations can improve their domestic footprint while shifting more resource-intensive activities to poorer

countries.

2.3. RTA's environmental clauses further reshape footprint dynamics

Given mounting concerns about the environmental impacts of trade liberalisation, RTAs are increasingly incorporating environmental provisions into their agreements. These clauses aim to balance economic integration with ecological sustainability by putting in place measures to prevent or reduce environmental damage linked to expanded trade. However, their effectiveness varies with the strength of the provisions, as illustrated in Fig. 2b. Studies shows that weak clauses act often as diplomatic tokens rather than real commitments, providing little protection against environmental harm (Jinnah and Morgera, 2013). On the other hand, strong and enforceable environmental measures, especially those with clear legal responsibilities and oversight, can help prevent the weakening of environmental regulations in the short term (Bastiaens and Postnikov, 2017). In some cases, these measures promote broader institutional reforms beyond the environmental domain (Kim, 2012; Postnikov and Bastiaens, 2014). Over time, these provisions can contribute to lasting environmental standards, provided there is sustained engagement from civil society (Marslev and Staritz, 2023; Tran et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, in the long-term, the real-world effectiveness of even the strongest clauses can be undermined by the adaptive strategies of both states and corporations. Studies have shown that companies can engage in regulatory arbitrage by relocating operations to countries with

Fig. 2. Theoretical pathways linking RTAs and environmental provisions to environmental outcomes. The causal mechanisms through which: (a) RTAs affect environmental performance in signatory countries across different levels of economic development (supporting hypothesis H2), and (b) environmental provisions in RTAs affect short- and long-term environmental outcomes (supporting hypothesis H3).

weaker enforcement, or resort to greenwashing by adopting surface-level environmental initiatives to conceal unsustainable practices (Nikou, 2025; Yang et al., 2020). Multinational corporations can further complicate matters by exploiting legal loopholes, restructuring supply chains, or using subsidiaries to avoid environmental responsibilities (Duan and Jiang, 2021; Ma et al., 2023). Moreover, the disjunction between top-down regulations and ground-level realities in producer countries can give rise to isomorphic mimicry, where institutions adopt the appearance of compliance without substantive change, thus reducing environmental laws to symbolic rather than transformative instruments (Kourtelis, 2021; Ye, 2020). Trade enforcement can also become politically sensitive when major allies are involved, as economic interdependence often deters punitive actions (Chen and Evers, 2023). Considering these dynamics, and the persistence of elevated global demand driven by affluent consumers, our third hypothesis is therefore:

H3: *While strong environmental clauses in RTAs can help reduce the outsourcing of environmental footprints in the short term, their effectiveness may diminish over the long term.*

3. Methods

3.1. Data

We used three broad categories of data in our analysis: (1) RTAs, which include bilateral and multilateral trade agreements, and the strength of environmental provisions; (2) natural resource consumption and the flow of resource footprints between countries globally; and (3) country socioeconomic and geographical characteristics, such as GDPs, development status, total human population over time, physical locations, and regional membership. The source of these data and the references supporting their use in our analysis are provided in Appendix A.

RTA data were obtained from the World Trade Organisation's (WTO) Regional Trade Agreements Database (2024). The data include all 634 trade agreements signed since 1948, as well as key information such as the RTA name, status (inactive, in force, or early announcement), date of signature, date of entry into force, bilateral or multilateral status, and signatory countries (including the original and current signatories). In this study, we analysed 420 RTAs from 1990 to 2018, encompassing all trade arrangements (FTA, CU, EIA, and PSA). Data on the strength of environmental provision in RTAs during the same period were obtained from a recent study by Santika et al. (2024), which are provided as supplemental materials in the relevant publication. The environmental provisions in each trade agreement were evaluated according to expert evaluations on a scale of very weak, weak, medium, and strong. These scales were developed based on four key criteria: (1) a description of the commitments made to environmental protection and/or sustainable development; (2) a special chapter dedicated to the environment, forest products, and/or biodiversity; (3) a review of the trade agreement's environmental impact; and (4) measures and support to address environmental issues. 'Very weak' RTAs are categorised as those that include minimal elements of criteria 1. 'Weak' RTAs are those that satisfy criteria 1 and at least some components of criteria 2. 'Medium' RTAs are those that fulfil criteria 1 through 3, while 'strong' RTAs meet all four criteria. A summary of the evaluation of each criterion into different scales is shown in Table S1 in the Supplementary Information.

Data on natural resource use and the transfer of resource footprints across countries were acquired from the UNEP-supported SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024). The database was built on the GLORIA (Global Resource Input-Output Assessment) model (Lenzen et al., 2022, 2017), and it is the most extensive MRIO (Multi-Region Input-Output) database to date, involving resource consumption and flows between 195 nations worldwide, providing a complete estimate of a country's consumption footprints from domestic sources (insourcing) and those imported (outsourcing). The SCP-HAT database provides yearly data from 1990 to 2018. While the database contains multiple

indicators of resource footprints and impacts, we focused on four of them for this study, including primary energy (in joules), raw materials (in tonnes), blue water (in cubic meters), and land use (in hectares).

Country-level statistics on socioeconomic indicators, such as the annual change in GDP per capita and economic status from 1990 to 2019, were obtained from the World Bank database (2024). The economic status of a country is classified into four categories: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), lower-middle-income countries (LMICs), and low-income countries (LICs). The change in total human population in each nation over the same period was acquired from the UN Population Division Data Portal (2023). Each country's physical location was represented by the geographical position of its capital city, with data collected from the World Cities database. The data were used to calculate the distance between nations in terms of trade. Although commodities can enter and exit a nation from a variety of locations, a vast majority of operations are likely to take place close to the capital. Data on nation regional membership was obtained from the UN Statistics Division (2023), which includes five broad regions: Africa, America, Asia, Europe, and Oceania.

3.2. Analysis

Our analyses were organised into three main themes, which corresponded to the three study objectives (and the corresponding hypotheses) that we sought to address. The analytical approaches we used for each theme is described below and were investigated for all four resource types: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

3.2.1. Trends in resource consumption and trade globally, regardless of RTA

The first research objective was to assess hypothesis H1, specifically: (1a) the patterns of natural resource consumption in different countries globally, irrespective of resource origin; (1b) the patterns of natural resource consumption by resource origin (insourced vs. outsourced); and (1c) the patterns of resource outsourcing of countries in relation to the socioeconomic characteristics of the trade participants. The hypothesis underlying each assessment, along with supporting references and the datasets utilised for evaluation, is summarised in Table A1 in Appendix A.

3.2.1.1. Evaluation 1a. To conduct evaluation 1a, we used the SCP-HAT consumption data as well as country-level human population and economic status data. We undertook a descriptive analysis by visualising the yearly change in per capita resource consumption from 1990 to 2018, separated by country economic level (HICs, UMICs, LMICs, and LICs). To estimate the trends in resource consumption per capita over time for each country's economic level j , we fitted an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to the log scaled data, i.e.

$$\log(RF_{i,t,j}) = \alpha_{0,j} + \alpha_{1,j}YEAR_t, \text{ for } \forall j \in \{HICs, UMICs, LMICs, LICs\} \quad (1)$$

where $RF_{i,t,j}$ denotes the overall per capita resource footprints (regardless of origin) of country i belonging to economic level j at time t , $YEAR_t$ denotes the year at time t , and $\alpha_{0,j}$ and $\alpha_{1,j}$ are the OLS model parameters to be estimated for each country's economic level j . To show the global fair share of resource use, we additionally computed the average consumption rates worldwide for each year.

3.2.1.2. Evaluation 1b. To undertake evaluation 1b, we also used the SCP-HAT and country-level human population and income status data. A descriptive analysis was performed by visualising the per capita resource consumption by country's economic level, total vs those outsourced, for three time periods from 1990 to 2018.

3.2.1.3. Evaluation 1c. To undertake evaluation 1c, we used the SCP-HAT data as well as country-level statistics on human population, GDP

per capita, and distance between countries. We employed a gravity model to analyse per capita resource outsourcing, considering the GDPs of both the home and outsourced countries, the geographical distance between them (Chaney 2018), and the year to account for global events potentially influencing trade (e.g., wars) (Zhu et al., 2024). We fitted a semi-parametric Generalised Additive Model (GAM) (Hastie, 2017) with a smoothing function to the data (in log scale), i.e.

$$\log(IRF_{i,j,t}) = f_1(YEAR_t) + f_2(GDPC_{i,t}) + f_3(GDPO_{i,j,t}) + f_4(DIST_{i,j}) \quad (2)$$

$IRF_{i,j,t}$ represents the per capita resource outsourcing of country i to country j at time t , $YEAR_t$ denotes the year variable. $GDPC_{i,t}$ represents the per capita GDP of home country i at time t , while $GDPO_{i,j,t}$ represents the per capita GDP of outsourced country j as a partner of country i at time t . $DIST_{i,j}$ represents the distance between home country i and outsourced country j . Lastly, f denotes the smoothing function estimated by the GAM.

3.2.2. The effect of RTAs on countries' footprints, whether outsourced or insourced

The second research objective sought to evaluate hypothesis H2 or the effect of RTA participation on the resource footprints of nations, specifically those that were (2a) outsourced, or (2b) insourced. The intervention under evaluation is RTA participation. Table A2 presents a summary of the hypotheses underlying each assessment, accompanied by corresponding references and the datasets employed for their evaluation.

3.2.2.1. Evaluation 2a. To conduct evaluation 2a, we used the RTA data, SCP-HAT consumption statistics, country-level human population, GDP, and economic status, as well as distance between countries. We applied a DID approach with matching to compare changes in footprint outsourcing between pair of countries before and after an RTA went into effect, to those in which the countries did not have an RTA. We ensured that the GDPs of the country pairs, their distance, the years when the change in footprints was analysed, and the baseline footprint outsourcing before RTA signing were all comparable. The analytical framework is illustrated in Fig. 1a, with each step explained below.

Step 1. Create pools of treated and control units from the data. We initially filtered the SCP-HAT data to include only countries that outsource their resource footprints to others. For the treatment group, we selected pairs of trading countries that had implemented an RTA for two years. The control group consisted of pairs of countries that did not have an RTA during the same period.

Step 2. Find a matched control for each treated unit. For each treated unit, we identified a matching case from the control group that shared the same home country but had a different outsourcing partner. We ensured that the partner had similar characteristics to the treated unit, including GDP, geographical proximity to the home country, and the extent of outsourcing three years before. We applied nearest neighbour matching with replacement by simulating various calliper width to achieve sufficient covariate balance between the treated and control units across all relevant covariates.

Step 3. Estimate the RTA effect on the matched dataset. We fitted an OLS model to the matched dataset to estimate the impact of RTA on the change in countries' footprint outsourcing (in log scale), i.e.

$$\log(IRF_2) - \log(IRF_{-1}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TA \quad (3)$$

IRF_2 denotes the extent of footprint outsourcing two years following RTA implementation, while IRF_{-1} denotes the extent of outsourcing a year before the RTA came into force. TA denotes a binary variable representing the treatment (RTA) and control (no RTA) status. A significantly positive β_1 value indicates that countries with RTAs are associated with greater outsourcing of footprints compared to those without RTAs, while a significantly negative value suggests the opposite. In addition to evaluating the overall impact of RTAs, we also explored

the heterogeneity of RTA effects across countries with varying economic levels, including HICs, UMICs, and LMICs and LICs jointly.

Step 4. Perform robustness checks. We employed diagnostic tests to assess the quality of the matching, including examining the density distribution of the treated and control units before and after matching (Fig. S1), quantifying the standardised mean differences (SMD) between the treated and control units of the post-match data (Table S2), and the bias reduction from the pre-match to post-match dataset (Table S2). For each relevant covariate, bias reduction was calculated as $100 \cdot (B_{pre} - B_{post}) / B_{pre}$, where B_{pre} and B_{post} are the percentage bias before and after matching, respectively. Percent bias B was calculated as: $100 \cdot (\mu_t - \mu_c) \cdot (0.5 \cdot (\sigma_t^2 + \sigma_c^2))^{-0.5}$, where μ_t and μ_c are the mean of treated and control units, and σ_t and σ_c are the standard deviation of the treated and control units. $SMD < 0.1$ implies good overlap between treatment and control units, whereas higher bias reduction suggests more effective matching procedure. The post-match datasets had $SMD < 0.058$ and a substantial improvement over the pre-match data in the region of overlap between the treatments and controls for all controlled variables (with bias reductions of 94.2%, on average) (Table S2; Fig. S1).

3.2.2.2. Evaluation 2b. To conduct evaluation 2b, we used RTA data, SCP-HAT consumption statistics, and country-level human population and GDP data. We employed a DID method with matching to analyse changes in footprint insourcing of countries before and after RTA, comparing them with countries that did not have an RTA. We ensured comparability between these countries in terms of GDP, baseline insourcing prior to the RTA, and the years during which the changes in footprints were assessed. Fig. 1b depicts the analytical framework, with each step described in detail below.

Step 1. Create pools of treated and control units from the data. The SCP-HAT data was filtered to include information on countries' footprint insourcing. We selected cases with an RTA in place for two years as treated units, and cases without an RTA as the control group.

Step 2. Find a matched control for each treated unit. To match each treated unit with a control, we identified cases from the relevant control pools that shared similar country characteristics, including GDP and the level of insourcing footprints three years prior. Nearest neighbour matching with replacement was employed by simulating various calliper width to achieve sufficient balance between the treatment and controls for all relevant covariates.

Step 3. Estimate the RTA effect on the matched dataset. We fitted an OLS model to the matched dataset to estimate the effect of RTA on the change in countries' footprint insourcing (in log scale), i.e.

$$\log(DRF_2) - \log(DRF_{-1}) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 TA \quad (4)$$

DRF_2 represents the extent of insourcing footprint two years post-RTA implementation, while DRF_{-1} indicates the extent of insourcing one year prior to the RTA. TA is a binary variable denoting treatment (RTA) and control (no RTA) status. A significantly positive γ_1 suggests that the RTA increases footprint insourcing, whereas a negative value indicates a decrease.

Step 4. Estimate the effect of the number of RTA-connected nations.

While the previous step compared the impact of RTA presence versus absence, it is noteworthy to investigate how the number of countries linked through RTA influences footprint insourcing. To investigate this, we applied an OLS model to the matched data, i.e.

$$\log(DRF_2) - \log(DRF_{-1}) = \delta_0 + \delta_1 NTA \quad (5)$$

DRF_2 represents the extent of insourcing footprint two years post-RTA implementation, while DRF_{-1} indicates the extent of insourcing one year before. NTA refers to the number of producing countries linked to a nation through an RTA. In addition to assessing the overall impact of RTAs, we examined the economic heterogeneity across countries. HICs and UMICs were analysed collectively, as were LMICs and LICs, to highlight the general differences between these two economic levels.

Step 5. Perform robustness checks. Diagnostic tests were employed to assess the quality of the matching, including examining the density distribution of the treated and control units before and after matching (Fig. S2), quantifying the standardised mean differences (SMD) between the treated and control units of the post-match data, and the bias reduction from the pre-match to post-match dataset (Table S3). The post-match datasets had $SMD < 0.035$ and a substantial improvement over the pre-match data in the region of overlap between the treatments and controls for all controlled variables (with bias reductions of 89.5%, on average) (Table S3; Fig. S2).

3.2.3. The effect of RTAs' environmental provisions on footprint outsourcing

The third research objective aimed to assess hypothesis H3 or how the strength of environmental clauses in RTAs influences the extent of footprint outsourcing by countries. The key intervention is the strength of environmental provisions within RTAs. We used RTA data, RTA's strength of environmental provision dataset, SCP-HAT consumption data, country-level human population, GDP, and economic status, as well as distance between countries. Table A3 outlines the hypothesis that guides our assessment, supported by relevant sources, and accompanied by the datasets used to evaluate it.

We used a DID approach with matching to compare changes in countries' footprint outsourcing before and after the implementation of RTAs with "strong" or "medium" environmental provisions, relative to countries with RTAs that include "weak," "very weak," or no environmental provisions. We ensured comparability between the countries in terms of GDP, distance, baseline outsourcing prior to RTA signing, and the years during which the changes in footprints were assessed. The analytical framework is shown in Fig. 1c, with each step explained below.

Step 1. Create pools of treated and control units from the data. We began by filtering the SCP-HAT dataset to concentrate on country pairs where outsourcing take place. For the treated units, we selected pairs of trading countries that had implemented an RTA with "strong" or "medium" environmental provisions for at least two years. For the control group, we chose pairs of trading countries that had an RTA with "weak," "very weak," or no environmental provisions during the same period.

Step 2. Find a matched control for each treated unit. For each treated unit, we identified a matching unit from the control group that was from the same home country but had a different outsourcing partner. We ensured that the partner had comparable characteristics to the treated unit, including GDP, geographical proximity to the home country, and the extent of outsourcing three years earlier. To achieve sufficient covariate balance between the treated and control units, we applied nearest neighbour matching with replacement by simulating various calliper widths.

Step 3. Estimate the RTA's environmental provisions on the matched dataset. We applied an OLS model to the matched dataset to estimate the impact of the strength of environmental provisions in the RTA on countries' outsourcing of their environmental footprint (in log scale), i.e.

$$\log(IRF_2) - \log(IRF_{-1}) = \theta_0 + \theta_1 EP \quad (6)$$

IRF_2 represents outsourcing footprints observed two years after the implementation of the RTA, while.

IRF_{-1} reflects outsourcing footprints one year before. EP is a binary variable that indicates the treatment group (RTAs with "strong" or "medium" environmental provisions) and the control group (RTAs with "weak," "very weak," or no environmental provisions). A significantly positive value of θ_1 suggests that RTAs with "strong" or "medium" environmental provisions are linked to greater outsourcing of footprints compared to those with "weak," "very weak," or no provisions, whereas a negative value implies lower outsourcing.

Step 4. Perform robustness checks. Diagnostic tests were performed to assess the robustness of the post-match data by assessing the region of

overlap between the treated and control units (Fig. S3) and quantifying the SMD and bias reduction (Table S4). The post-match datasets had $SMD < 0.098$ and a substantial improvement over the pre-match data in the region of overlap between the treatments and controls for all controlled variables (with bias reductions of 83.5%, on average) (Table S4 and Fig. S3 for two and four years after the RTA implementation).

4. Results

The results are structured according to the three research questions or hypotheses we aimed to evaluate. We begin by presenting our findings on global trends in resource footprints and trade, independent of RTA, focusing on overall footprint patterns and by resource origin. Next, we describe how RTAs affect the footprints of countries, distinguishing between outsourced and insourced resources. Finally, we present how the stringency of environmental clauses in RTAs affect footprint outsourcing and their long-term effectiveness. A more detailed discussion of the implications of these findings is provided in the Discussion section.

4.1. What are the trends in natural resource use and trade globally, regardless of RTA?

The extent of a country's natural resource footprints for primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use, both sourced domestically and externally, corresponds systematically to its level of economic growth (Fig. 3). The highest per capita footprints were found in HICs, followed by UMICs, LMICs, and LICs, respectively. Between 1990 and 2018, HIC per capita consumption of primary energy was constantly at four times the global average of $71.3 \text{ GJ person}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3a; Table S5), while consumption by UMICs, LMICs, and LICs decreased by 1.7–1.8% each year (Table S6). In recent periods, primary energy consumption in LMICs and LICs fell sharply below the global average, with current consumption accounting for barely a-third and one-tenth of the global average, respectively. In terms of raw material consumption, HICs used three times the global average of $10.4 \text{ tonnes person}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ over the last three decades, whereas LMICs and LICs fell short, with current consumption per capita representing only half and a quarter of the global average, respectively (Fig. 3b; Table S5).

Per capita consumption of blue water and land use footprints decreased across all country types in the last three decades (Fig. 3c-d; Table S5). This is most likely because the world's land and water supplies are finite, and as the population expands, the quantity of resources available per person decreases. Nonetheless, HICs' blue water footprints remain one-and-a-half the global average of $155.6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ person}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, and land use footprints are twice as large (Table S5). Yet, the blue water footprints of LMICs and LICs are currently only half and one-fifth of the global average, respectively, while the land use footprint is equal to the global average (Table S5). The global trends thus reveal a growing disparity in natural resource use between wealthier and poorer nations.

HICs not only have much higher overall consumption rates than other country types, but they also exhibit a significantly greater proportion of outsourced environmental footprints compared to those that are insourced (Fig. 4). Between 1990 and 2018, HICs outsourced 75% of their total primary energy consumption, whereas UMICs, LMICs, and LICs outsourced less than 67% (Fig. 4a). Additionally, HICs outsourced 68% of their raw materials during this period, while the other country types outsourced less than 49% (Fig. 4b). Similarly, in HICs, outsourcing accounted for 81% of blue water consumption and 72% of land use, whereas for other country types, outsourcing made up less than 65% of blue water consumption and less than 35% of land use (Fig. 4c-d).

A gravity model revealed that extent of footprint outsourcing generally increase proportionally to a country's GDP and its geographical proximity to the countries to which outsourcing occurs (Fig. 5). In terms of resource exports, countries can be primary energy exporters

Fig. 3. Resource footprint by countries' economic status. Left: The change in resource footprint of countries with varying economic levels: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), low-middle-income countries (LMICs), and low-income countries (LICs), in terms of (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use, annually between 1990 and 2018. Red lines indicate the consumption trends for each economic level (with P denoting the p-value of the trend's slope over time), while blue lines indicate the average or fair share of the global resource uses. Right: Long-term average (1990–2018) of resource footprint of countries by economic status relative to the global fair share. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

regardless of their GDP levels (Fig. 5a). However, countries with GDPs below \$1,000 are more likely to export raw materials than those with higher GDPs (Fig. 5b). Moreover, as the GDPs of countries decline, the exports of blue water and land use tend to rise (Fig. 5c-d). These findings suggest that resource flows are driven by a disparity in economic power, with higher-GDP countries predominantly importing resources from lower-GDP countries, highlighting the unequal nature of global trade in resource footprints.

4.2. Does RTA affect countries' outsourcing and insourcing of resources footprints?

Between 1960 and 2020, as many as 520 RTAs were signed, with 320 RTAs in force by 2020 with the EU leading the way with 77 RTAs. Trade agreements have boosted international ties between nations during the last 60 years. Between 1960 and 1980, the average number of countries with which a nation had trade agreements was just 7, with Western European states having the strongest linkages to 45 other countries

(Fig. 6a) spanning four continents (Fig. 6b). Between 1980 and 2000, the average number of countries with whom a country has trade agreements increased to 24, and between 2000 and 2020, it increased to 38, with EU member states having the greatest ties to over 85 countries across five continents.

Following two years of the RTA's implementation, we found that, in comparison to countries without any RTA links, the scale of footprint outsourcing from signatory countries increased dramatically (Fig. 7a). Participating nations in RTAs were linked to increased outsourcing of primary energy by 12.5% (95% Confidence Interval (CI) 1.5–24.8%) compared to non-RTA countries, raw material by 18.6% (CI 6.8–31.7%), and land use footprints by 27.2% (CI 13.8–42.1%), but not in blue water footprints (Table B1 in Appendix B). These patterns were similarly observed in HICs, with the outsourcing of primary energy increased by 11.6% (CI -1.2–25.9%), raw material by 13.6% (CI 2.6–25.7%), and land use footprints by 33.5% (CI 13.8–56.5%). On the other hand, in UMICs only the raw material outsourcing increased (Table B1). The patterns of outsourcing in primary energy, raw materials, and land use

Fig. 4. Resource footprint by countries' economic status, total and outsourced. Resource footprint of countries in terms of (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use, and the volume and percent share of those imported (outsourced). Countries are broken down by economic level: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), low-middle-income countries (LMICs), and low-income countries (LICs). Error bars represent the 95 % confidence intervals. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

among HICs were largely driven by their transfer of production to LMICs and LICs (Table B2).

RTAs not only benefit consuming nations by increasing access to imported resources, but it also allows these countries to preserve their local natural resource endowments. Our findings showed that after two years of RTA participation, the consumption of locally sourced primary

energy, especially for higher-income countries (HICs and UMICs), reduced by 48.3% (CI 0.1–73.6%) compared to countries without RTA involvement, and the consumption of local blue water reduced by 15.4% (CI 0.5–28.1%) (Table B3). The greater the number of countries linked to consuming countries through RTAs, the larger the reduction in consuming countries' reliance on their domestically sourced natural

Fig. 5. Imported resources in relation to the trade participant's socioeconomic features. The extent of imported or outsourced footprint, including (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use, in relation to yearly variation, the distance between consumer and producer countries involved in trade (in log scale), and the GDPs of these countries (in log scale), estimated using a gravity model. Shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval of the curve (fitted by the Generalised Additive Models). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

resources. For every increase in the number of countries linked through RTAs, higher-income countries were able to reduce insourcing of primary energy by 3.6% (CI 0.1–7.0%) and blue water by 2.3% (CI 0.8–3.8%) (Fig. 7b; Table B4). This indicates that the RTA ties allow consuming countries, especially those with strong economies, to retain their domestic resources while offshoring their footprints overseas.

4.3. Do environmental provisions in RTAs affect countries' outsourcing of environmental footprint?

Between 1980 and 2020, there were 455 RTAs signed; of these, 82.2% were deemed to have no or very weak environmental clauses, 15.2% to be weak, and 2.6% to be medium or strong. RTAs with a “weak” environmental clause first emerged in 1995, while those with “medium” and “strong” clauses first appeared in 2000 and 2009, respectively, indicating a desire to make environmental provisions more stringent in RTAs. The EU and the US are the most common signatories to RTAs with “medium” and “strong” environmental provisions.

Our analysis revealed that the strength of environmental provisions in RTAs yielded mixed outcomes across various footprint indicators. Following the adoption of RTAs for two years, the outsourcing of raw materials by countries with environmentally stricter RTAs decreased by

15.3% (CI 5.7–24.0%) in comparison to those from nations with weaker RTAs of similar characteristics. Nevertheless, the outsourcing of land use increased by 22.8% (CI 11.1–35.8%) (Fig. 7c; Table B5). The outsourcing of primary energy and blue waters is unaffected by the stringency of RTA's environmental provisions. Nonetheless, a longer-term evaluation conducted up to four years after the implementation of the RTA shows that the effectiveness of the stricter regulations decreased over time (Fig. 7c; Table B5). This suggests that businesses may have rapidly adapted, reducing the effect of the regulatory constraints.

5. Discussion

Here, we discuss the implications of the findings presented in the Results section. We begin by addressing the asymmetrical nature of trade influenced by power imbalances among nations with differing economic positions. Subsequently, we discuss how RTAs amplify existing inequalities among member countries, followed by a discussion of the limited long-term effectiveness of the environmental provisions within RTAs. Finally, we outline the limitations of our analysis and suggest potential avenues for future research and improvement.

Fig. 6. Expansion of trade agreements. Trade agreements connecting (a) countries and (b) regions globally, and their expansion over three time periods between 1960 and 2020.

5.1. Ecologically unequal exchange under global economic inequality

The relationship between international trade, economic growth, and environmental sustainability is complex and often subject to debate. While trade is often viewed as a way to promote prosperity and sustainable development (World Bank 2018; OECD 2023), the broader socio-ecological effects are posing substantial challenges, particularly when considering the disparities in economic baselines across different nations globally (Althouse et al., 2023; Bruckner et al., 2023). Our gravity model shows that, regardless of RTA, resource imports are stronger when the importing country's GDP is higher, and the exporting country's GDP is lower. This emphasises the unbalanced nature of trade and global value chains, and the power inequalities that exist between countries of differing economic positions (Althouse et al., 2023).

Higher income levels boost purchasing power, increasing demand for resource-intensive goods such as electronics, cars, and processed foods, which require significant energy, materials, land, and water to produce. This leads to higher per capita resource footprints in wealthier populations. Affluent nations exemplify these consumption patterns, but also tend to adopt ambitious environmental policies as public demand for environmental public goods increases (Fredriksson et al., 2005). However, maintaining high consumption levels while pursuing environmental goals presents a challenge, unless there are places outside their country's borders where resource-intensive production may be outsourced to lessen domestic impacts (Berry et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the legacy of colonialism and geopolitical marginalisation have left many resource-rich countries burdened with

significant debt and constrained economic capacities, systemically entrenching their position as suppliers of raw materials and basic manufacturing within the global economy (Hornborg and Martinez-Alier, 2016; Infante-Amate and Krausmann, 2019). Early industrialised, wealthier nations, on the other hand, benefit disproportionately by importing inexpensive raw materials from less affluent countries and goods that cause pollution during their production in those countries, while exporting high-value products (Hornborg and Martinez-Alier, 2016; Infante-Amate and Krausmann, 2019). Our result supports previous research that estimates the annual net appropriation of over 10 billion tonnes of embodied raw materials from poorer countries through a process known as ecologically unequal exchange (Dorninger et al., 2021). The impact of resource consumption in richer nations being offshored to poorer countries and the net appropriation of resources from these countries generates an annual flow of \$10 trillion. This amount represents a loss to poorer nations that is thirty times greater than the value of foreign aid they receive (Hickel et al., 2022).

5.2. RTAs amplify existing inequalities among participating countries

Our analysis further reveal that the growth of RTAs appears to be aggravating the impact of existing power imbalances among participating nation. It enables wealthier consuming countries to enhance the preservation of some of their domestic resources while offshoring their footprints abroad, a process known as environmental impact or burden shifting (Akizu-Gardoki et al., 2021; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023). Under such circumstances, certain regions or countries bear the

Fig. 7. Impact of RTA and environmental provision on countries' footprint outsourcing and insourcing. (a) The effect of RTA participation on countries' footprint outsourcing, (b) the effect of the number of countries linked via RTAs on footprint insourcing, and (c) the effect of environmental provisions' stringency in RTAs on countries' footprint outsourcing through time. For (c), the effect was estimated as the difference in the change of countries' footprint outsourcing (in log scale) under 'medium' or 'strong' RTAs compared to those under 'weak', 'very weak', or no environmental provision within one to four years of RTA implementation. The assessment of primary energy was limited to three years of RTA implementation due to insufficient matched data for estimation. Error bars represent the 95% confidence intervals. The notation below each bar indicates the significance level: ●●● p-value < 0.001, ●● p-value < 0.01, ● p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1, and ns for non-significance.

environmental and social costs of resource extraction for the benefit of more economically powerful nations (de LT Oliveira and Hecht, 2017; Zografos and Robbins, 2020). Our findings corroborate a number of previous studies evaluating the environmental impact of RTAs, indicating that RTAs increase environmental impact shifting from wealthy to poorer nations (Jönsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023), although our analysis is based on more comprehensive data and empirical models.

The shifting environmental impact in wealthy countries, driven by the rise of RTAs, highlights a paradox for global sustainability. Outsourcing pollution and resource depletion creates a misleading sense of environmental progress, as these nations report lower domestic emissions and resource use while their consumption continues to inflict

environmental damage abroad. As Requena-i-Mora and Brockington (2021) highlight, many affluent countries achieve high rankings on the Environmental Performance Index (EPI), which focuses exclusively on domestic environmental improvements, despite their substantial consumption levels and extensive material footprints derived from overseas (Fanning et al., 2022). As data enabling the tracing of resource use to its origin becomes increasingly available (Lenzen et al., 2017), it is imperative to adopt more comprehensive metrics that incorporate environmental performance both within and beyond national borders, such as Carbon Footprint and Material Footprint indices (Lenzen et al., 2022). Reliance on naïve indices in the context of a globalised world risks undermining the essence of the UN SDGs.

5.3. RTAs' environmental provisions have limited long-term effectiveness

The emphasis on environmental clauses in RTAs is an attempt to address the repercussions of increasing trade. While our analysis did find that stricter environmental provisions serve as a short-term remedy for the import of certain resources, such as raw materials, they have not proven effective beyond two years of the adoption. We found that stricter environmental provisions had negligible or worsening effects on imported footprints for primary energy, blue water, and land use, regardless of the timeframe. Our findings contradict previous research, which found environmental provisions to be effective (Abman et al., 2024; Berger et al., 2020; Brandi et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2017). However, it is noteworthy that most of these studies assessed commodity imports or environmental outcomes only within the first or second year following the implementation of environmental provisions. A recent study by Presberger and Bernauer (2023), who used a similar dataset to ours but employed a different methodological approach and examined outcomes one-year post-RTA implementation, also found that resource outsourcing reduced with environmental provision, albeit marginally.

Our findings on the limited long-term impact of RTAs' environmental provisions may be attributed to several factors. Recent studies have determined that the majority of RTAs incorporating stricter environmental provisions do not significantly surpass weaker RTAs or those lacking such provisions, and these provisions often remain ambiguous in terms of sustainability obligations (Hradilová and Svoboda, 2018; Morin and Jinnah, 2018). Beyond the specific clauses within RTAs, studies examining individual cases in greater detail have highlighted critical limitations. While some mandatory standards have been established, these agreements often lack robust legal frameworks to enforce environmental protections and include insufficient dispute resolution mechanisms to ensure compliance with sustainability standards (Baccini, 2019; Friel et al., 2020; Heyl et al., 2021; Martínez-Zarzoso et al., 2023). Furthermore, under conditions of consistently high or increasing demand for commodities, businesses may prioritise capitalising on market opportunities. Consequently, there are strong incentives to disregard or deliberately circumvent regulations to expedite production processes (Carvalho et al., 2019; Lyon and Maxwell, 2019). This dynamic may lead to a gradual decline in the efficacy of environmental provisions over time.

5.4. Study caveats and future research

Our study has several limitations that present opportunities for future research. We did not examine the environmental impact of individual sectors. Certain sectors, such as energy and agriculture, may have significantly higher resource consumption compared to others, even within the same trade region (Johnson et al., 2021; Mantoam et al., 2020). Gaining sector-specific insights could help design targeted interventions, such as promoting sustainable production practices or reducing emissions in high-impact industries. Evaluating the effects of specific trade agreements could also highlight opportunities for more effective bilateral or multilateral cooperation. A more detailed analysis of the environmental provisions in RTAs would also help us better understand how certain policies either support or hinder the mitigation of environmental impact shifting. Such insights could help countries within RTAs work together more meaningfully to tackle shared environmental challenges and promote collective accountability for environmental degradation (Bowen et al., 2017; Muradian et al., 2025).

Additionally, we did not examine the differences between North-South and South-South trade agreements. Lechner and Spilker (2022) observed that environmental clauses within South-South trade agreements are increasingly common and, contrary to earlier assumptions, demonstrate greater efficacy in reducing air pollution emissions among participating nations than those in North-South agreements. Several previous research reported similar findings (Brandi et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2017). This enhanced effectiveness may stem from a shared

recognition among southern nations of the concrete societal impacts associated with climate and environmental change, contrasting with the more abstract perceptions common in northern countries (Hase et al., 2021; McAllister et al., 2024; Olausson and Berglez, 2014).

Furthermore, our analysis of flows between nations and regions shows inequalities between countries with different economic statuses but does not address the unequal distribution of consumption among different socioeconomic groups within nations. Despite increases in per capita incomes and the associated consumption emissions over the last decades, which have helped to create a global middle class and allowed millions to escape poverty in developing countries, the world's richest households in wealthier nations have continued to emit more (Chancel, 2022; Nielsen et al., 2024). Nearly half the growth observed has merely allowed the already wealthy top 10% to augment their consumption and enlarge their carbon footprints, with all the damage this entails. Historical and ongoing inequality will pass down to future generations, unless more efforts are made to reduce the continued outsized impact of the minority group of the world's wealthiest individuals, wherever they reside, as well as addressing the continuing development needs and aspirations of the world's poorest citizens (Kantha et al., 2020).

6. Conclusion

The evidence presented in this article reinforces other sources that demonstrate the stark inequalities in international trade, involving significant flows of resource from poorer to wealthier nations and the outsourcing of negative environmental impacts. By employing more rigorous data and analytical methods, we provide new evidence that this outsourcing of environmental impacts is intensifying, with increasing RTAs driving higher resource transfers in recent decades. While stricter environmental provisions in RTAs have been introduced as a short-term measure, they have proven neither sufficient nor sustainable. The growing demands of affluent nations further challenge the long-term effectiveness of such measures. Concurrently, poorer nations, which serve as the primary suppliers of global resources, are increasingly burdened by climate change, exacerbating their vulnerability to the cycle of resource exploitation and socio-ecological harm. Broader evidence indicates that environmental degradation and climate change pose increasing barriers to economic growth, while there is insufficient evidence supporting the feasibility of green growth decoupling at the scale, speed, and permanence required (Hickel and Kallis, 2020; Infante-Amate et al., 2024). This underscores the urgent need for deliberate shifts to tackle overconsumption, rising inequality, and ecological harm.

Affluent nations need to reduce their material consumption to mitigate the socio-ecological impacts of resource extraction in less affluent countries. Engaging in open dialogue about imposing absolute limits on consumption, guided by the principles of material sufficiency, may offer a constructive path forward. As highlighted by Dunlop and Völker (2023), achieving sustainability requires a clearer understanding of what defines "needs" and "enough" in the context of consumption, enabling us to reshape material supply and consumption systems accordingly. Achieving meaningful sustainability transformations will demand not only the adoption of degrowth strategies but also comprehensive structural reforms to the global financial architecture (Dempsey et al., 2024; Ghosh et al., 2025). In parallel, integrating environmental footprint data into assessments of a country's environmental performance is essential for mitigating biases that disproportionately benefit high-consumption nations that rely on outsourcing production. As such data becomes more accessible, these metrics can better align national environmental performance with the UN SDGs, particularly Goal 12 (responsible consumption and production). Reforming RTAs to incorporate ecological footprint accountability and establish resource-equity mechanisms, such as ecological premiums on resource-intensive imports, represents a critical step toward sustainable global practices. Finally, whilst our analysis shows that RTAs and current environmental measures often have negative or limited effects, this should not be seen

as an argument for isolationism or protectionism. Instead, we advocate for critically rethinking trade frameworks through the lens of ecological limits and distributive justice, ensuring that economic integration supports, rather than undermines, environmental sustainability and global equity.

7. Twitter

Counterfactual analysis over 3 decades shows that trade deals intensified environmental impact shifting. While stricter environmental clauses briefly curbed some footprints, effects were short-lived.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Truly Santika: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Valerie Nelson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jeremy Hagggar:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Indika Thushari:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation.

Appendix A

The tables below provide a summary of the analyses carried out in this study, the hypotheses or underlying rationale guiding the investigation, supported by pertinent references, and the datasets employed to evaluate these hypotheses.

Table A1

Analysis 1: Trends in resource footprints and trade globally, regardless of RTA.

<i>Analysis objective</i>	<i>Hypothesis or rationale underpinning the investigation, supported by relevant references</i>	<i>Datasets used to assess the hypothesis and their sources</i>
Evaluation (1a). Assess the patterns of resource consumption across countries, irrespective of resource origin.	The per capita environmental footprints of nations are typically positively correlated with their level of economic development (Wiedmann et al., 2015; Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020).	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country’s economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024)
Evaluation (1b). Assess the patterns of resource consumption across countries by resource origin (insourced vs. outsourced).	As nations experience economic growth, they often decrease the share of material extraction conducted domestically by relying more on imported (outsourced) resources (Wiedmann et al., 2015).	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country’s economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024)
Evaluation (1c). Assess the patterns of resource outsourcing across countries in relation to the socio-economic features of the trade participants.	Imported (outsourced) footprint generally increase proportionally with a country’s GDP and its geographical proximity to outsourced countries (Bruckner et al., 2023; Chaney, 2018; Wiedmann et al., 2015). Less affluent countries are more dependent on resource exports or basic manufacturing.	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country’s GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Distance between countries, measured as the distance between their respective capital cities. Source: World Cities database.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Truly Santika, Valerie Nelson, and Jeremy Hagggar reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe scheme. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Table A2
Analysis 2: RTA's effect on countries' footprints, whether outsourced or insourced.

Analysis objective	Hypothesis or rationale underpinning the investigation, supported by relevant references	Datasets used to assess the hypothesis and their sources
Evaluation (2a). Assess the impact of RTA on countries' footprint outsourcing.	RTAs can elevate the outsourcing footprints of countries (Jönsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023). The extent of footprint outsourcing by a country in a particular year can be influenced by various factors, including the GDPs of both the home and outsourcing nations (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020), the geographical distance between these countries (Chaney, 2018), and the timing (year) of trade influenced by global events (e.g., wars) (Zhu et al., 2024). These factors must be accounted for when evaluating the impact of RTAs on footprint outsourcing.	RTA data. Source: Trade Agreements Database (World Trade Organization, 2024) Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country's GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Country's economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024) Distance between countries, measured as the distance between their respective capital cities. Source: World Cities database.
Evaluation (2b). Assess the impact of RTA on countries' footprint insourcing.	RTAs can result in the shifting of environmental impacts, where a portion of the overall footprint is transferred to other countries, while simultaneously decreasing the domestic footprint (Jönsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023). The extent of domestic footprint (insourcing) by a country in a particular year can be influenced by various factors, including the country's GDP (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) and the specific timing (year), which may be influenced by global events (Zhu et al., 2024). These factors must be controlled when evaluating the impact of RTAs on footprint insourcing.	RTA data. Source: Trade Agreements Database (World Trade Organization, 2024) Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country's GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Country's economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024)

Table A3
Analysis 3: Environmental provision's effect on countries' footprint outsourcing.

Analysis objective	Hypothesis or rationale underpinning the investigation, supported by relevant references	Datasets used to assess the hypothesis and their sources
Assess the impact of stringent environmental clauses in RTAs on the outsourcing of footprint.	Environmental provisions in RTAs have the potential to minimise footprint outsourcing of countries (Abman et al., 2024; Brandt et al., 2020). The extent of footprint outsourcing by a country in a particular year can be influenced by various factors, including the GDPs of both the home and outsourcing nations (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020), the geographical distance between these countries (Chaney, 2018), and the timing (year) of trade influenced by global events (e.g., wars) (Zhu et al., 2024). These factors must be accounted for when evaluating the impact of RTA's environmental provision on footprint outsourcing.	RTA data. Source: Trade Agreements Database (World Trade Organization, 2024) RTA's strength of environmental provisions. Source: Santika et al. (2024) Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country's GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Country's economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024) Distance between countries, measured as the distance between their respective capital cities. Source: World Cities database.

Appendix B

Table B1
The estimated effect of RTA participation on countries' footprint outsourcing from 1990 to 2018, overall and broken down by countries' economic level: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), and low-middle-income and low-income countries (LMICs and LICs). Resource footprints evaluated include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter β_1 in Eq. (3), with 95% CI and p -value \neq)	
Overall			
Primary energy		12.54%	(1.51%, 24.76%) ●
Raw material		18.63%	(6.84%, 31.72%) ●●
Blue water		-1.71%	(-6.05%, 2.84%)
Land use		27.17%	(13.81%, 42.10%) ●●●
By countries' economic level			
Primary energy	HICs	11.57%	(-1.17%, 25.95%) +
	UMICs	19.93%	(-5.59%, 52.36%)
	LMICs and LICs	7.81%	(-14.51%, 35.97%)
Raw material	HICs	13.55%	(2.55%, 25.72%) ●
	UMICs	38.06%	(3.16%, 84.76%) ●

(continued on next page)

Table B1 (continued)

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter β_1 in Eq. (3), with 95% CI and p -value ‡)	
Blue water	LMICs and LICs	16.59%	(-16.37%, 62.56%)
	HICs	1.93%	(-5.37%, 9.80%)
	UMICs	-7.61%	(-16.18%, 1.85%)
Land use	LMICs and LICs	-2.98%	(-9.25%, 3.71%)
	HICs	33.50%	(13.84%, 56.55%)
	UMICs	2.80%	(-17.78%, 28.53%)
	LMICs and LICs	12.85%	(-7.77%, 38.09%)

‡ ●●● p -value < 0.001, ●● p -value < 0.01, ● p -value < 0.05, + p -value < 0.1.

Table B2

The estimated effect of RTA participation on countries' outsourcing of resource footprints from 1990 to 2018, categorised by the economic status of home and outsourced country pairs (with 95 % CI and p -value ‡). The assessed resource footprints include: (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use. A positive value indicates increased outsourcing. Bolded figures denote statistically significant effects.

(a) Primary energy		Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs	
HICs	16.72% (-43.62%, 141.65%) ns $n = 30$	-8.09% (-28.49%, 18.10%) ns $n = 68$	18.61% (3.50%, 35.95%) ●● $n = 204$	
UMICs	75.17% (-7.82%, 232.56%) + $n = 14$	-34.53% (-62.34%, 13.81%) ns $n = 46$	49.45% (16.09%, 92.38%) ●● $n = 58$	
LMICs/LICs	14.69% (-22.74%, 70.25%) ns $n = 16$	-21.57% (-42.37%, 6.76%) ns $n = 60$	19.47% (-31.06%, 107.03%) ns $n = 44$	
(b) Raw materials		Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs	
HICs	35.59% (-20.36%, 127.46%) ns $n = 22$	16.92% (-0.75%, 37.71%) + $n = 92$	17.83% (3.75%, 33.83%) ●● $n = 236$	
UMICs	84.14% (-4.62%, 250.48%) + $n = 38$	56.72% (2.51%, 139.62%) ● $n = 28$	2.21% (-31.57%, 52.68%) ns $n = 46$	
LMICs/LICs	81.21% (-25.41%, 340.21%) ns $n = 30$	-25.31% (-54.25%, 21.93%) ns $n = 32$	19.34% (-20.31%, 78.71%) ns $n = 44$	
(c) Blue water		Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs	
HICs	-0.07% (-5.66%, 5.86%) ns $n = 40$	-2.65% (-10.75%, 6.17%) ns $n = 128$	4.71% (-6.51%, 17.27%) $n = 270$	
UMICs	-18.32% (-30.95%, -3.40%) ● $n = 58$	-3.99% (-12.86%, 5.76%) ns $n = 68$	-1.38% (-22.76%, 25.91%) $n = 56$	
LMICs/LICs	0.81% (-3.63%, 5.46%) ns $n = 180$	-13.58% (-31.55%, 9.10%) ns $n = 78$	1.65% (-11.57%, 16.86%) $n = 92$	
(d) Land use		Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs	
HICs	-20.33% (-45.68%, 18.85%) ns $n = 28$	-16.13% (-32.57%, 0.15%) + $n = 108$	65.60% (33.11%, 106.02%) ●●● $n = 280$	
UMICs	1.72% (-30.84%, 49.62%) + $n = 40$	-32.03% (-54.08%, 0.68%) + $n = 50$	38.35% (-5.09%, 101.67%) + $n = 70$	
LMICs/LICs	47.35% (-1.41%, 120.25%) + $n = 28$	-9.47% (-36.52%, 29.08%) ns $n = 34$	8.83% (-17.47%, 43.50%) ns $n = 28$	

‡ ●●● p -value < 0.001, ●● p -value < 0.01, ● p -value < 0.05, + p -value < 0.1.

Table B3

The estimated effect of RTA participation on countries' footprint insourcing two years after the RTA implementation. Analyses were based on data between 1990 and 2018, and include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter γ_1 in Eq. (4), with 95 % CI and p -value ‡)	
Overall			
Primary energy		-29.86%	(-47.41%, -6.46%) ●
Raw material		-18.56%	(-34.31%, 0.96%) +

(continued on next page)

Table B3 (continued)

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter γ_1 in Eq. (4), with 95 % CI and p -value ‡)	
Blue water		4.58%	(-15.48%, 29.41%)
Land use		4.48%	(-10.13%, 21.46%)
By countries' economic level			
Primary energy	HICs and UMICs	-48.35%	(-73.58%, -0.06%) ●
	LMICs and LICs	-17.13%	(-35.68%, 6.78%)
Raw material	HICs and UMICs	-15.23%	(-41.05%, 21.89%)
	LMICs and LICs	-21.13%	(-38.85%, 1.71%) +
Blue water	HICs and UMICs	-15.42%	(-28.10%, -0.51%) ●
	LMICs and LICs	16.30%	(-14.84%, 58.82%)
Land use	HICs and UMICs	-1.93%	(-22.47%, 24.06%)
	LMICs and LICs	8.69%	(-11.73%, 33.84%)

‡ ●●● p -value < 0.001, ●● p -value < 0.01, ● p -value < 0.05, + p -value < 0.1.

Table B4

The estimated effect of the number of countries linked through RTA on footprint insourcing two years after the RTA implementation. Analyses were based on data between 1990 and 2018, and include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of the number of nations linked by RTAs (parameter δ_1 in Eq. (5), with 95 % CI and p -value ‡)	
Overall			
Primary energy		-2.87%	(-4.71%, -0.99%) ●●
Raw material		-1.06%	(-2.76%, 0.67%)
Blue water		-1.47%	(-2.92%, -0.01%) ●
Land use		-0.47%	(-2.69%, 2.82%)
By countries' economic level			
Primary energy	HICs and UMICs	-3.60%	(-7.01%, -0.06%) ●
	LMICs and LICs	-1.29%	(-3.44%, 0.89%)
Raw material	HICs and UMICs	-2.90%	(-6.27%, 0.59%) +
	LMICs and LICs	-0.52%	(-2.35%, 1.34%)
Blue water	HICs and UMICs	-2.31%	(-3.80%, -0.80%) ●●
	LMICs and LICs	-1.15%	(-3.15%, 0.90%)
Land use	HICs and UMICs	0.27%	(-1.08%, 1.64%)
	LMICs and LICs	-0.86%	(-4.40%, 2.82%)

‡ ●●● p -value < 0.001, ●● p -value < 0.01, ● p -value < 0.05, + p -value < 0.1.

Table B5

The estimated effect of the strength of environmental provisions in RTAs on countries footprint outsourcing between 1990 and 2018, after one to four years of RTA implementation. Resource footprint evaluated include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. Shading for primary energy means that there was limited matched dataset to estimate the impact of RTAs' environmental provisions.

Footprint indicator	Years after RTA implementation	Estimated effect of RTAs' strength of environmental provisions (parameter θ_1 in Eq. (6), with 95 % CI and p -value ‡)	
Primary energy	One year	-11.07%	(-23.84%, 3.85%)
	Two years	5.98%	(-8.35%, 22.55%)
	Three years	73.62%	(11.38%, 170.62%) ●
	Four years		
Raw material	One year	-22.13%	(-29.54%, -13.95%) ●●●
	Two years	-15.33%	(-24.00%, -5.66%) ●●
	Three years	-0.04%	(-13.22%, 15.14%)
	Four years	22.81%	(-20.30%, 89.23%)
Blue water	One year	6.05%	(-0.50%, 13.04%) +
	Two years	1.46%	(-5.64%, 9.10%)
	Three years	5.16%	(-7.89%, 20.04%)
	Four years	23.96%	(2.39%, 50.08%) ●
Land use	One year	14.61%	(5.92%, 24.01%) ●●●
	Two years	22.80%	(11.09%, 35.76%) ●●●
	Three years	32.07%	(15.65%, 50.82%) ●●●
	Four years	44.20%	(24.23%, 67.38%) ●●●

‡ ●●● p -value < 0.001, ●● p -value < 0.01, ● p -value < 0.05, + p -value < 0.1.

Appendix C. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2025.103028>.

Data availability

All data utilised in this study have been previously published. The sources of these datasets are provided in Appendix A of the manuscript.

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